

Critical Infrastructure Protection in the Banking Sector

A 2030 Outlook

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1. Introduction

Banks constitute a core pillar of a country's economy in terms of managing and facilitating daily transactions among individuals as well as organisations. They ensure the financial stability of a country through enabling commerce and supporting societal well-being. Through the digitalisation of services and modern ways of financial transactions such as the introduction of cashless payments, banks have become an imperative part of today's economy. According to the European Central Bank¹, in the second half of 2023, the total number of non-cash payments in the euro area increased by 6.6% reaching 71.2 billion, while the total number of contactless card payments increased to 23.2 billion. In parallel, banks play an important role in financing businesses at different scale, in order to facilitate their daily operations as well as supporting their growth, considering that the financial system in Europe is largely bank-based². A strong dependency has been created between the stability of the daily workflows of a society and the banking organisations operating within this origin, requiring operational resilience throughout their whole infrastructure.

During the last decade and especially during and after the COVID-19 era, banks undergo a heavy digital transformation in order to meet the requirements of the continuously changing regulation and their customers' needs. However, the introduction of new technologies and operational processes may be accompanied by vulnerabilities that malicious actors may exploit towards their financial benefit, which constitutes the most common motive. Online services, remote onboarding, higher volume of transactions, mobile banking have increased the attack surface, while physical security breaches and insider threats are still present. Banks are guided by introduced regulations to incorporate appropriate security measures, however social engineering still constitutes one of the most prevalent mechanisms followed by fraudsters³.

Protecting the infrastructure of the banking sector is not just important, it is part of the national security. This white paper focuses on analysis the existing challenges that the banking sector is facing in terms of Critical Infrastructure Protection, the gaps that have been identified which require proactive measures towards ensuring resilience, while outlining constructive guidelines and recommendations from the perspective of the different involved stakeholders, with the uttermost goal to strengthen the resilience of the banking sector.

¹ https://www.ecb.europa.eu/press/stats/paysec/html/ecb.pis2023_1~10a5662f81.en.html

² <https://www.euro-area-statistics.org/digital-publication/statistics-insights-money-credit-and-central-bank-interest-rates/bloc-2b.html>

³ https://www.splunk.com/en_us/blog/learn/social-engineering-attacks.html

2. Challenges

Following the alignment of the Critical Infrastructure Protection for the banking sector, this section focuses on outlining and describing the challenges faced by the industry in terms of safeguarding its critical infrastructure. These challenges are categorised into specific areas such as cybersecurity threats, complexities related to the regulatory requirements, risks introduced by third-party solutions and providers, physical security risks and challenges associated with the existing and the emerging technologies incorporated in the banking sector. The analysis below will familiarise the reader with the challenges faced by the banks, identify the gaps and finally describe potential recommendations and guidelines.

2.1. Cybersecurity Threats

Considering the aggressive digitalisation that has taken place over the last years, in order to keep up with the changes in the regulations and to maintain competitiveness across the banking landscape, various technologies were and have to be incorporated, which may potentially introduce certain cyber threats. In the meantime, leveraging the evolvement of technology, fraudsters and criminals have moved their attacks online where they exploit the technology itself by performing cyber-attacks or through exploiting the human factor in the overall process.

- **Phishing and Social Engineering.** This constitutes one of the most common attacks applied by fraudsters, where they exploit the human factor. Banking systems enforce strong security measures both at their backend systems as well as at the endpoint level, building security across every level of the banking ecosystem. Bypassing each of these levels of security require strong know-how as well as deep knowledge on the vulnerabilities of the overall ecosystem. Nevertheless, in many cases humans constitute the weakest point of the security chain. Thus, instead of trying to infiltrate a very secure fortress, fraudsters tend to focus their effort on tricking the customers of the banks in various ways in order to get access to their financial accounts, having as an ultimate goal to acquire their financial savings. One of the most common approaches is *phishing*, where through luring SMS or email messages they redirect the customers to fraudulent look-a-like websites, where customers are tricked to input their credentials to their bank account. In a similar way, the customer may download a malicious software that could enable the fraudster to receive remote access to the device. *Social engineering* constitutes another approach followed by fraudsters. The customer of the bank is commonly approached by fraudsters impersonating either investment brokers in order to perform a very appealing investment or support from large tech companies indicating that their device is part of a cyber-attack. In both cases, the customer of the bank becomes the victim and provides remote access to the fraudster through tools like AnyDesk or TeamViewer. Once the fraudster is granted remote access to the device of the victim, the fraudster either directly performs transactions to a fraudulent account or guides the victim itself to perform the fraudulent transaction.
- **Sophisticated Attacks on Digital Infrastructure.** Banks enforce strong security measures in order to prevent attacks on their digital infrastructure. Among others, this includes periodical checks and updates for vulnerable software components, isolation and restriction of accessibility of various backend systems through the internet, intelligent firewalls, regular software updates etc. These security measures focus primarily on reducing the attack surface for fraudsters. However, one of the attacks that still constitutes a challenge

for organisations including banks are the attacks following the approach of Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) as they threaten the availability and integrity of banking operations. These attacks are performed in a distributed manner, originating from multiple sources, having the uttermost goal to lead the backend systems of the banks to reach a certain point that they cannot serve the customers of the banks anymore. These attacks create an increased load of traffic to the digital infrastructure of the bank, in a distributed manner, which is highly difficult to be detected. Due to the increased traffic at the backend systems of the banks, these systems reach their serving capability limits and are not able anymore to serve the requests performed by the legitimate customers, putting the bank's infrastructure out of service. The distributed nature, where the requests come from multiple source, makes these attacks difficult to be detected.

- **Ransomware and Malware Attacks.** A less common type of attacks in the banking sector are those based on ransomware and malware. During such type of attacks, the banking infrastructure is infected through ransomware and malware and the banking systems become encrypted and not accessible until the bank pays a certain amount to the fraudsters. In other cases, fraudsters are granted access to the banking systems through malware and perform different types of fraudulent activities and transactions. However, there are attacks that are very seldom nowadays. The occurrence of such types of attacks takes place primarily on systems that leverage outdated software, do not have installed updated antivirus solutions and do not perform regular updates to their infrastructure. Nowadays banks, through their certifications and regulation, have introduced endpoint device management solutions that incorporate rules for automated updates. These solutions ensure compliance with the rules, keeping the endpoint devices of these organisations updated and less vulnerable to existing security threats. Furthermore, introduction of two-factor authentication as well as remote access through virtual private network (VPN) strengthens the security of the systems even more.

2.2. Regulatory Complexity

The regulatory framework for the banking sector is continuously changing in order to keep up with customer needs, the technological evolution and in particular to cope with the growing and unprecedented fraud cases and cyber-attacks. These regulations constitute the core basis on how the internal operational processes are structured towards managing personal data, performing financial transactions, monitoring and detecting potential cyber and physical threats. In addition to the introduced processes, the regulatory frameworks are often followed by the appropriate training to the personnel of the banks as well as the incorporation of relevant technology to improve the monitoring and detection of potential fraud cases.

- **Evolving Compliance Requirements:** Financial authorities at the European (e.g. European Banking Authority) and the national level continuously monitor the evolution of the banking sector especially on sensitive aspects such as the use and protection of personal data (e.g. General Data Protection Regulation), citizens privacy, the process of performing financial transactions (e.g. Payment Services Directive 2) as well as the common and the upcoming fraud cases and fraud numbers across Europe and at national level. Through monitoring these key aspects of the banking sector, these authorities, in order to protect EU citizens, introduce new regulatory frameworks in terms of security and privacy mechanisms. However, often these mechanisms come at the expense of the user friendliness and the

customer satisfaction. Thus, banks often are placed in the position of having to balance the trade-off between the security and privacy mechanisms against the user experience of the citizens.

- **Cross-Border Regulatory Coordination:** As banks scale their operations and expand as organisations, they move from national region, to international. Even though the banks across Europe follow the regulations introduced by the European Banking Authority, each country incorporates its own national banking authority that may introduce its own regulatory requirements. In this way, in case a banking organisation expands across multiple European countries, there is a need to perform cross-border regulatory coordination, in order to enable the organisation to comply with the regulatory framework at the national level. In case, the banking organisation scales across different continent, then additional effort is required to perform regulatory coordination across the different continents.

2.3. Third-party Risks

There is an ever-increasing demand of parameters that today's banks need to cope with including the regulatory compliance, further development of user-centric services, maintenance of existing infrastructure and services as well as customer support. This are just a few of the elements that bank have to perform and in parallel to innovate. It creates a huge demand and stress to the operational capacity of the banks, towards supporting such a large range of activities. In the meantime, there are organisations and start-ups that focus specifically on one or a few of the aforementioned elements, having acquired particular expertise in these areas, and ultimately offering a plug-n-play service. Thus, banks adopt external software tools and solutions in order to keep up and stay ahead of the competition. Furthermore, hiring the appropriate team is not an easy task, given the volatility in the market nowadays. Hence, services such as customer support are often outsourced considering that setting up an internal customer support requires large effort to build from scratch. However, even though the banks enforce internally strong security processes, although detailed vetting of the vendors take place, the incorporation of third-party organisations and solutions to the bank, may introduce certain cybersecurity risks.

- **Supply Chain Dependencies.** In order to improve the quality and security of their offered services, modern banks introduce more and more third-party solutions. This could include anti-fraud systems, payment processing, core and mobile banking and many more. Instead of reinventing the wheel, banks integrate third-party solutions with focused expertise on a specific element, and which have been often adopted by other organisations, thus ensuring certain level of reliability and robustness. Creating such partnerships with organisations having focused expertise, banks pave the way towards operational efficiency and scalability. However, particular attention should be paid during the vetting process of such third-party solutions to ensure that appropriate security, technical and operational measures are in place. In case strong security measures are not applied, vulnerabilities could be introduced to the bank's ecosystem, creating a security risk for the financial and personal information of the bank customers.
- **Outsourcing Risks.** Particular operations that require the involvement of human personnel such as customer support and anti-fraud monitoring are costly require significant effort in recruitment and managing the workforce. These operations come with significant upfront costs due to the 24/7 nature of their requirements and there is also a need to factor in the cases

where people will be on leave, thus additional personnel must be available. Furthermore, scalability is also important, as during specific periods of time across the year or during unprecedented times, a large number of customers may require support (e.g. during Christmas holidays, in case the banking system malfunctions). In such cases, the customer support of the bank needs to be able to cope with the workload and support the increased volume of requests. For the above-mentioned reasons, banks perform outsourcing of such operations. However, this may introduce various security risks and personal data leakage due to lack of security standards and compliance measures, impacting customers' trust and satisfaction.

3. Gaps and recommendations

Following the performance of the analysis of existing and upcoming threats and risks related to the banking sector, these have led to the identification of industrial gaps with respect to the critical infrastructure. These are gaps that arose during the analysis of the existing banking landscape and ecosystem exploring the volatile risks and vulnerabilities of the banking organisations.

- **Fragmented Threat Intelligence.** Banks often operate in silos in order to protect their interests, maintain internally the strategies followed by each of the organisations including the information related to fraud cases that each of the banks experience on a daily basis. Even though banks have to report to the national authority periodically, the fraud cases that take place and the intelligence about the ongoing fraud and the tools used to mitigate these threats are kept internally, lacking a collaborative approach towards defending against these risks.
- **Inadequate Incident Response Planning.** Even though banks go through particular certifications that are required in order to receive and maintain a banking license, due to the size of the organisations it is often observed that the incident response planning are not well planned and tested. These incident response plans, in consequence of the size of the organisations and the exposure they have as critical infrastructure, constitute an important aspect of the overall risks of each of the organisation and for that reason should be periodically and rigorously tested to ensure the effectiveness of these plans.
- **Underinvestment in Security.** Security constitutes a department in a banking organisation that requires continuous investment to defend the bank against potential existing and upcoming threats. Strong security is required by the regulation and assists to increase of customer trust towards the bank. However, it does not introduce any direct revenue stream to the bank. Considering that businesses perform investments with the sole purpose to increase the current revenues of the organisation and receive a return on investment (ROI); in security this is not the case as there is not direct or tangible ROI. For this reason, security experts in banks often find themselves difficult in justifying an investment in security and the ROI it will create.
- **Regulatory Gaps.** Regulations arise through well-researched and discussed elements and co-creational workshops of experts, incorporating multiple revisions and feedback from the public. However, this process requires significant time in order to meet the needs of the involved stakeholders, while minimising the disruption and the adoption process. The inevitable consequence is that during this process changes may take place in the industry as well as new threats and risks may arise, creating regulatory gaps due to the timely process of shaping the regulatory frameworks.

- **Lack of Operational Resilience.** A common approach followed by banking organisations is strengthening the monitoring and detection mechanisms for particular risks and threats. However, limited effort is placed on ensuring the operational resilience after a particular event has taken place. Considering there is no bulletproof approach for detecting and preventing fraud, banking organisations should place additional effort on ensuring the operational resilience in recovering from specific attacks or events.
- **Technological Obsolescence.** Banking systems often are defined by complex architectures and are composed by multiple subsystems either legacy or updated. In cases where banks' processes are still based on legacy systems, they often lack the appropriate security mechanisms required by today's software artefacts. Furthermore, considering the criticality of banking systems and the long vetting and sales cycles experienced in the banking sector, adoption of novel emerging technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and blockchain is quite slow.
- **Workforce Skills Gap.** As the security threats and risks emerge, it is evident that detection and prevention solutions require skilful personnel, capable of managing such solution as well as being knowledgeable to understand and act accordingly to mitigate these risks. Cybersecurity has become an essential aspect, where each of the employees of a bank should receive the appropriate training towards identifying such risks and informing the experts inside an organisation to initiate the relevant mitigation processes.

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